

The Music Sources of Daniel Auber in Victor Gsovsky's Grand Pas Classique: A Research Note

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1. The problem

Victor Gsovsky's *Grand Pas Classique* entered the repertory on 12 November 1949, when it was performed at the Theatre des Champs-Élysées by Yvette Chauviré and Vladimir Skouratoff. It has remained in circulation ever since and is now a familiar part of the international classical repertory. Yet for all its fame, the origins of its musical material have usually been described only in very general terms. Most programmes and reference works are content with the formula "music by Auber"; more rarely, one encounters a more specific but, apparently, mistaken attribution linking the score of Gsovsky's pas de deux to *Le Dieu et la Bayadère*.

Some sources do point in other directions. In its review of Richard Bonyngé's recording of *Marco Spada* with the London Symphony Orchestra (January 1976), *High Fidelity* states that the music of *Grand Pas Classique* "is derived from *Marco Spada*". In his introduction to *The Ballets of Daniel-François-Esprit Auber*, Robert Ignatius Letellier connects the music of the pas de deux not only with *Marco Spada* but, at a deeper level, with *Fra Diavolo*, *Le Duc d'Olonne* and *The Grand Exhibition Overture*. Yet even there the issue is not a section-by-section attribution of *Grand Pas Classique* itself, but rather the wider genealogy of its musical material.

A more specific pointer comes from a brief remark by Dario Salvi in the booklet notes to his recording of Auber. Speaking of the Act IV pas de deux in the 1857 opéra-ballet version of *Le Cheval de bronze*, he observes that this music is familiar from the opening of Gsovsky's *Grand Pas Classique*. The importance of this remark lies not in the fact that it offers a finished attribution already absorbed into ballet scholarship, but in the way it points to a particular number within *Le Cheval de bronze* and so helps to direct further research. As far as one can judge, this source has not yet been clearly brought into the discussion in ballet literature on the music of *Grand Pas Classique*.

None of these texts, however, offers a full and precise section-by-section attribution of the number. The aim of the present note is to fill that gap and to

establish a detailed map of the musical sources of Victor Gsovsky's *Grand Pas Classique*.

2. Sources and method

This study is based on comparison of the musical text of *Grand Pas Classique* with the scores, répétiteurs, vocal scores, printed librettos and audio recordings of Auber's works available to the author. The comparison was carried out against the score of *Le Cheval de bronze*, the score, répétiteur and libretto of *Marco Spada* (1857), the vocal score of *Le Dieu et la Bayadere* (1831), and Richard Bonyngne's 1972 recording of *Marco Spada* with the London Symphony Orchestra.

What was compared in each case was not just the thematic material, but the place of a passage within the dance form: its metre, key, sequence of sections, and any cuts or omissions.

3. Results of the comparative analysis: the sources of *Grand Pas Classique* by section

Comparison of the sources yields the following map of the number:

Entree and adagio - *Le Cheval de bronze*, Act IV, pas de deux for Amalia Ferraris and Louis Mérante.

Male variation - *Le Cheval de bronze*, Act IV, second variation from the pas de deux for Amalia Ferraris and Louis Mérante.

Female variation - *Marco Spada*, Act II, Pas de Mlle Ferraris: Ferraris's variation.

Coda - *Marco Spada*, Act II, Pas de deux Rosati et Petipa; not from the same number as the female variation.

The entree, adagio and male variation of *Grand Pas Classique* were therefore borrowed by Gsovsky from the Act IV pas de deux in the opéra-ballet version of *Le Cheval de bronze* (1857). The female variation and coda, by contrast, belong to *Marco Spada*, but not to the same number. In the score of *Marco Spada*, the female variation can be identified as Amalia Ferraris's variation in the Pas de Mlle Ferraris within the Act II divertissement. The coda belongs to the following pas de deux in the same divertissement, the Pas de deux Rosati et Petipa.

This matters because it shows that, in drawing on the musical material of the Act II divertissement in *Marco Spada*, Gsovsky combined passages from two different numbers rather than transferring one continuous musical sequence into his own pas de deux.

4. The deeper genealogy of the themes

In some cases, the musical fragments assembled by Gsovsky for his pas de deux can also be found in other works by Auber. This is because Auber himself occasionally reused the same theme in more than one composition.

The material of the first and third sections of the adagio from *Le Cheval de bronze* reappears later in the Grande ouverture pour l'Exposition de Londres (1862). Yet the middle section of the adagio is absent from that overture, as is the entrée. The 1862 overture therefore matters not as the immediate source of Gsovsky's adagio, but as evidence of Auber's later self-borrowing.

A similar situation may be observed in relation to *Marco Spada*. At a deeper level, the music of the female variation used by Gsovsky goes back to Zerline's solo episode in Act I of the Italian version of *Fra Diavolo*. The immediate source for *Grand Pas Classique*, however, is not the opera as such, but the ballet number already refashioned in Act II of *Marco Spada*. Something similar can be seen in the coda. One of its principal ideas appears earlier in the overture to *Le Duc d'Olonne*, but *Grand Pas Classique* does not take it from there directly: it comes through the later ballet reworking in *Marco Spada*.

What matters here is the distinction between two things: the immediate source of the pas de deux as a dance form, and the deeper history of the individual themes that make it up.

5. On the origin of the *Le Dieu et la Bayadere* error

The present analysis shows that the attribution of Gsovsky's pas de deux to music from *Le Dieu et la Bayadere* is not borne out by the original musical sources. The error most likely goes back to the E.F. Kalmus music edition, for which William McDermott prepared a new orchestration: it is in distributor descriptions of that edition that one finds the claim that Gsovsky borrowed the music from Auber's 1830 opera *Le Dieu et la Bayadere*. In fact, *Grand Pas Classique* was assembled from ready-made dance structures by Auber, borrowed

from two of his 1857 stage works: the Act IV pas de deux from *Le Cheval de bronze* and two pas de deux from the Act II divertissement of *Marco Spada*.

6. Conclusion

This study allows the musical nature of *Grand Pas Classique* to be described more precisely. Although Auber is the composer of this pas de deux, he did not conceive it in exactly this form. In the original sources, the entree, adagio, male variation, female variation and coda belonged to different numbers, and indeed to different ballets.

Grand Pas Classique thus emerges as a carefully assembled composite score. What matters, however, is that the fragments from which it is built had already been written or reworked by Auber himself as ballet music: as entree, adagio, variations and coda. In other words, Gsovsky was not turning vocal or instrumental themes into music for a pas de deux afresh; that work had already been done by Auber. It was from these ready-made dance fragments that Gsovsky assembled the score of a new pas de deux. Identifying the specific musical fragments and the stage works from which Gsovsky borrowed them not only corrects the attribution of the score of *Grand Pas Classique*, but also shows that one of the most famous concert pas de deux of the twentieth century rests on genuine nineteenth-century ballet structures, thereby preserving a living connection with Auber's almost vanished stage works.

Sources cited

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